

Table 2 continued.

Treatment (dS m ⁻¹)	Genotypes				
	BH-5-89	BH-3-89	RST-1-86	RST-2-84	Bas370XNR-1
10 (NaCl)					
Chl a	0.300 (71)	0.310 (73)	0.163 (54)	0.222 (58)	0.357 (90)
Chl b	0.370 (76)	0.405 (62)	0.172 (23)	0.297 (61)	0.354 (83)
Chl t	0.670 (74)	0.615 (67)	0.335 (39)	0.519 (59)	0.711 (87)

^aChl a = chlorophyll a, Chl b = chlorophyll b, Chl t = chlorophyll (total). ^bValues in parentheses show % of control.

and RST-2-84 had the lowest chlorophyll content of the five genotypes.

Biomass production is a function of photosynthetic efficiency (Terry and Waldron 1984), which is decreased because of the decrease in leaf area and chlorophyll. A decrease in leaf area causes a reduction in area for light

interception and absorption of the specific wavelength necessary for photosynthesis. The results of this experiment showed that NaCl is more toxic and injurious than mixed salts and that BH-5-89, BH-3-89, and Bas370 are more tolerant of salt stress and RST-1-86 and RST-2-84 are sensitive to salt stress.

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Crop management

A labor-saving technique in direct-sown and transplanted rice

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The Cauvery Delta zone accounts for about 22.3% of the rice area and 25.3% of rice production in Tamil Nadu State. Rice is cultivated in three distinct seasons—*kuruwai* (Jun-Oct), followed by *thaladi* (Oct-Feb) in double-crop

wetlands and *samba* (Sep-Jan) in single-crop wetlands.

Transplanting continues to be the major method of crop establishment for rice in this area. It requires more labor, time, and efforts. The scarcity and high cost of farm labor invariably delay transplanting and often lead to the use of aged seedlings. Uncertain release of water from the Mettur dam aggravates the situation for seedling age and time of transplanting.

Because of these problems, many rice farmers wish to switch to direct seeding under puddled conditions.

Besides reducing labor requirements, it can help to shorten the growth cycle from seeding to maturity. Experiments were conducted during 1995-96 and 1996-97 at the TNRRI to evaluate wet seeding for establishing rice crops.

The methods of crop establishment—transplanting (S1), sowing sprouted seeds in lines manually (S2), and using a seed drum (S3)—were compared. The drum seeder used in this trial was developed by the Department of Agricultural Engineering, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Coimbatore. The 8-row drum seeder

Table 1. Effect of crop establishment methods on yield and economics of rice, 1995-96.

Treatment	Days to 50% flowering		Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)		Straw yield (t ha ⁻¹)		Net return (Rs ha ⁻¹)		Return Re ⁻¹ invested	
	Kuruwai ^a	Thaladi	Kuruwai	Thaladi	Kuruwai	Thaladi	Kuruwai	Thaladi	Kuruwai	Thaladi
Transplanting (S1)	85.8	105.6	5.5	4.8	6.6	5.1	16,165	11,982	2.32	1.98
Sowing sprouted seeds in lines manually (S2)	78.6	98.6	5.5	4.9	6.7	5.3	16,561	13,545	2.47	2.20
Drum seeding of sprouted seeds (S3)	78.9	98.7	5.6	5.0	6.8	5.3	17,836	13,960	2.65	2.29
CD (P = 0.05)	0.62	0.55	ns ^b	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	0.204	ns

^aKuruwai = Jun-Oct, thaladi = Oct-Feb. ^bns = not significant.

Table 2. Effect of crop establishment methods on yield and economics of rice, 1996-97.

Treatment	Days to 50% flowering		Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)		Straw yield (t ha ⁻¹)		Net return (Rs ha ⁻¹)		Return Re ⁻¹ invested	
	Kuruvai ^a	Thaladi	Kuruvai	Thaladi	Kuruvai	Thaladi	Kuruvai	Thaladi	Kuruvai	Thaladi
Transplanting (S1)	85.9	105.4	5.9	5.0	7.2	5.5	17,542	12,813	2.40	2.02
Sowing sprouted seeds in lines manually (S2)	78.8	98.5	5.8	5.2	7.4	5.7	18,303	14,657	2.58	2.27
Drum seeding of sprouted seeds (S3)	78.9	98.7	6.0	5.3	7.4	5.7	19,453	15,046	2.75	2.30
CD (P = 0.05)	0.62	0.55	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	0.180	0.172

^aKuruvai = Jun-Oct, thaladi = Oct-Feb. ^bns = not significant.

requires only 9 kg of pulling force to operate. The machine weight is 11 kg without seed and 19 kg with seed (2 kg seed hopper⁻¹). It requires 14 person-h to cover 1 ha.

Direct seeding reduced the time to 50% flowering by 7 d in both the kuruvai and thaladi seasons in both years (Tables 1 and 2). The delay in flower emergence by 1 wk in transplanted rice might be due to the transplanting shock experienced by the seedlings.

The methods of crop establishment showed no significant influence on grain yield of rice in both the kuruvai and thaladi seasons in both years of study. In both seasons, however, drum seeding gave a slightly higher grain yield. A similar trend was noticed in the case of straw yield. Yield parameters such as number of panicles, panicle length, number of filled and immature grains, and 1,000-grain weight were not affected by the method of crop establishment.

Net savings averaged Rs 1,911 (US\$47) and Rs 2,233 (US\$56) ha⁻¹ in the drum-seeding method versus the transplanting method in the kuruvai and thaladi seasons, respectively. The drum-seeding method required only 8 person-h whereas line sowing of sprouted seeds and transplanting methods required 200 and 400 person-h ha⁻¹, respectively. There is thus a significant savings of labor in the drum-seeding method. ■

Optimum seedlings per unit area for high-yielding rice varieties in the hill zone of Karnataka

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Rice is the major field crop grown during monsoon under rainfed conditions in the hill zone of Karnataka (located between 11° 56' and 15° 46' north latitude and 74° 31' and 76° 4' east longitude). For improved low- and midland rice cultivation, 20 × 10-cm spacing (50 hills m⁻²) is being recommended for improved rice varieties. Adoption of this recommendation by farmers was low on the grounds that the number of seedlings recommended per m² was too high.

To verify whether the number of seedlings per unit area could be reduced, an experiment was conducted with the popular high-tillering variety

Intan during 1993 and 1994. The experiment was continued during 1995 and low-tillering, high-yielding, blast-tolerant variety DWR 4107 (Hemavati) was included. DWR 4107 has been released to replace Intan in high-blast pressure areas of the zone.

A randomized block design replicated four times was employed in 1993 and 1994. A split-plot design was employed in 1995 with varieties as main plots and plant spacing as subplots. In addition to the recommended spacing, an additional four spacings were used to produce 45, 40, 35, and 30 hills m⁻². Depending on climatic factors, nursery sowing and transplanting varied over the years. Sowing and transplanting were done in Jul 1993. Sowing was done in Jun 1994 and 1995 and transplanting was done in Jul 1994 and Aug 1995. Net plot size was 12.5 m² during 1993 and 1994 and 9.6 m² during 1995. Recommended P (33 kg P ha⁻¹) and K (72.6 kg K ha⁻¹) along with 50% N (37.5 kg N ha⁻¹) were applied at the time of

transplanting and the balance of N was topdressed in two splits at 30 and 60 d after transplanting. There was no need for plant protection measures in any of the 3 yr.

Compared with 1993 and 1995, grain yield of Intan was significantly higher in 1994 (see table) because sowing and transplanting were done on time during that year. The seedlings were not sufficiently aged in 1993 and they were overmatured in 1995 (see table). Grain yield from the recommended 50 seedlings m⁻² was significantly different from that produced by 30, 35, 40, and 45 seedlings m⁻² each year, indicating that a similar grain yield could be obtained by adopting wider spacing, accommodating as few as 30 seedlings m⁻². There were significant differences between treatments for other characters, but these differences were not reflected in grain yield.

A pooled analysis over the 3 yr indicated that there was a significant increase in tillers plant⁻¹ and panicles